

Kinship on the Dancefloor: Music, Loneliness and Social Connection on Melbourne's Gay Scene

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Abstract

Loneliness is a growing social and public health issue, and inadequate social connection can be as damaging to health as smoking 15 cigarettes per day (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2010). Identity is understood to play a key role in mediating social connection (Haslam et al., 2020) and socially vulnerable groups are particularly at risk, including migrants, the elderly, and LGBTQIA+ people (Eres et al., 2021). It is well established that music engagement offers potential for enhancing social connection (DeNora, 2013), and the concept of 'scene' has been used in popular music studies as a way of explaining music's role in mediating local, trans-local, and virtual social connections (Bennett & Peterson, 2004). This paper integrates qualitative interviews and personal, auto-ethnographic data generated during a research project at the University of Melbourne into a reflective essay on the ways music can mediate social connection for gay men on the Melbourne gay scene, giving particular focus to the venues in and around the suburb of Collingwood, and opportunities the scene provides to generate kin-like relationships in the perceived absence of other opportunities to do so, such as via parenthood. It considers the emerging insights in relation to various dimensions of social connection and contrasting notions of queerness, some of which emphasise the importance of identity as an aspect of queerness, while others view normative identity categories as the problem (Sullivan, 2003). This autoethnographic essay points towards some of the varieties of social value that music holds for gay men on the Melbourne scene, and some of the ways that intra-community connections can be musically delineated.

Before my father, Hugh Kiernan, died in 2016 of blood cancer, after making the brave decision to turn off his own dialysis machine, throw himself a party, and walk into the mouth of death with his head held very high, he self-published a book of short stories called *Love Letters from Transylvania* (Kiernan, 2015). The book is a memoir of sorts, an account of his long acquaintance with the disease. In the preface, Richard Freadman, a professor of English at La Trobe University, described the book as “one of the most eloquent and compelling cancer memoirs ever written in Australia” (p. vii). The book contains a passage in which dad describes standing on Rathdowne Street, outside Melbourne’s Cancer Council building, after a tearful encounter with a cancer nurse, silently squinting into the Western sun, refusing to look away. “A version of me is still there,” he wrote (p. 89). I’ve thought a lot about that sentence since he died, and sometimes I go to that spot, and I think of him, and I feel his presence there. And sometimes I wonder about how it can be that our “selves”, or at least, parts of ourselves, become bound to certain places.

This essay discusses some of the emerging findings of a qualitative study which set out to explore how music can help mediate social connection among LGBTQIA+ people in Victoria, Australia. And so it might seem odd that I’ve started with a rather emotional anecdote about my father’s death. But working on this project has intersected with many aspects of my personal life in ways that I didn’t expect it to, and this has led to a methodological shift in emphasis, away from my initial plan to conduct large-scale surveys and interviews about music engagement in my community, towards an auto-ethnographic approach that makes use of the researcher’s own experiences in the field that is the focus of study (Poulos, 2021). Working on this project has helped me understand why, for example, when I found out my father had cancer, I ran, as soon as the weekend arrived, to a gay nightclub called The Market, which was then on Commercial Road in Prahran, around the corner from where I was living at the time. In my seat at the bar, next to Andrew, the kind doorman who had come to find me, I started my process of anticipatory grief, and not one minute before. The gravity that pulled me towards that nightclub is one that has pulled me towards gay and queer venues, in Melbourne, Berlin, London, and other cities I have lived in, for decades, and it still does, though less often as I get older; I turned 42 shortly before writing this essay.

The project, which received Human Research Ethics approval from the University of Melbourne (ID: 25195), is revealing, through in-depth interviews, ethnographic observation and auto-ethnographic reflection, a variety of forms of attachment that gay men, in particular, have to different venues and spaces where queer people gather in music to be together, such as bars, nightclubs, and parties. I initially planned to use a case-study approach, discussing

individual venues one by one, but it's now clear that I'm talking about a whole scene, a cluster of music venues, spaces and events geographically located in and around the suburb of Collingwood, but which extends, in a metaphysical sense, far beyond that.

It is partly a response to the COVID-19 pandemic, during which Melbourne endured a world record 245 days of lockdown (Boaz, 2021). This highlighted something that public health researchers already knew well: people fare poorly when isolated, and strategies for addressing what had already been termed a “loneliness epidemic” are much needed, particularly for LGBTQIA+ people and other socially vulnerable groups, who are at higher risk (Eres et al., 2021). Loneliness is associated with a variety of adverse health outcomes, both physical and mental, including cardiovascular disease, depression, cognitive decline, and even a 26% increase in the risk of premature mortality (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Rico-Uribe et al., 2018).

In psychology, loneliness is typically understood as a subjective feeling of distress in response to dissatisfaction with the quality or quantity of one's social relationships, or, in other words, “perceived social isolation” (J. T. Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009). Various dimensions or types of loneliness have been conceptualised at different levels of social interaction, from personal and intimate forms of loneliness, through broader social and relational forms, right up to collective and existential varieties of loneliness, which relate to our public networks of social identities and our sense of belonging in the world (for examples, see S. Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nobel, 2023). One model proposed by Stephanie Caccioppo and her colleagues in 2015 describes how different dimensions of loneliness map onto corresponding dimensions of attentional space, and the culturally inflected ways people use their bodies in those spaces as described in Edward Hall's theory of proxemics (Hall, 1966), and I will return to this point about culturally shaped uses of the body below. These approaches have been useful for the current study, for example, as prompts guiding interview discussions, however I am also informed by approaches outside of psychology, in which loneliness is often conceptualised as an emotion, rather than a subjective feeling (Alberti, 2019), in ways that emphasise its strategic function. Loneliness can, for example, be viewed as an *emotional practice*, in the sense meant by Pierre Bourdieu, using a framework developed by historical and cultural anthropologist Monique Scheer (2012). This view highlights the ways loneliness is something people learn how to do, over time and in context, a practice through which one positions oneself in relation to others in a given social field using the available resources. A body of literature in the history of emotion has emerged around this theoretical construct (Barclay, 2021).

The issue of loneliness as it relates to identity is particularly relevant to the current project, and the study of loneliness in LGBTQIA+ communities more broadly, because queer theory,

which is often used as a lens for understanding the identities and practices of people in these communities, treats queerness not as an umbrella term that refers to various identity-based groupings of same-sex attracted and gender diverse people, but as, in the words of David Halperin, “an oppositional relation to the norm” (Halperin, 1995, p. 62). In queer theory, “queer” refers to a deconstructive enterprise that shifts in relation to a shifting normative mainstream, seeking to challenge heteronormative ways of life including marriage and kinship family (Taylor, 2012). “Queer”, in this radical sense, is forever mobile, and it can never settle on or define an identity; as Lee Edelman puts it, “it can only ever disturb one” (Edelman, 2004, p. 17). In this paradigm, social connection resembles a promise, the promised result of reconceptualised identities, power dynamics and discursive relations beyond binaries such as man/woman, and gay/lesbian. Researchers in the social sciences, of course, often take a different view, arguing that social identity is a basis for social connection, wherein individuals internalise broader group identities into their sense of self, thereby bringing those group members closer in a psychological sense, and indeed, rendering them extensions of the self (Haslam et al., 2020). We see this in the social connections that arise through shared group membership in support of sporting teams, for example, or in the process by which Taylor Swift’s fans become a legion of “Swifties”. Various attempts have been made to find productive intersections between queer theory and psychology (Ben Hagai & Zurbriggen, 2022), and between queer theory and sociology (Seidman, 1996; Compton et al., 2018), with varying degrees of success. Insofar as social connection is a basis for health, the health of LGBTQIA+ people hangs on the tension between these opposing approaches to understanding social connection and the role of identity in it.

Music engagement offers potential for mediating and strengthening social connections, and promoting health and wellbeing more generally, as a wealth of evidence from various disciplines has shown (Ansdell, 2016; APPG, 2017; Baker, 2015). Tia DeNora’s (2013) sociologically oriented approach to explaining music’s capacities in his regard proposes that music can offer forms of “asylum”, or “respite from distress and a place and time in which it is possible to flourish” (p. 24). Music asylums entail two broad strategies, removal and refurbishing, where the former generates a sense of distance from one’s environment and helps to recover a sense of personal time and rhythm, while the latter involves creative, imaginative play, thus helping to remake or renegotiate social worlds. For DeNora, music’s impact on health and wellbeing takes shape gradually within an unfolding future time-space of undetermined quantity, in which the transformations that occur in the musical encounter resolve into new understandings. She calls this time-space music’s “future perfect”, by analogy

to the English grammatical tense, the tense in which one “will have done” something (p. 142). And so it follows that music, ontologically speaking, is understood to be not *only* a sonic structure unfolding in time, but as a cultural event, which is integrated, and preceded and followed, with social action that informs its meaning.

There is a long history of writing about the importance of musical spaces such as bars, nightclubs and parties for queer people. Much of this has focused on narratives of oppression and resistance (Branton, 2021), showing how these spaces offered refuge against intolerance and persecution, while offering opportunities to express oneself freely. More recently, the concept of the “scene” has emerged in popular music studies as a way of describing musical spaces for collective participation and belonging, and different kinds of “scene” have been identified, such as local, trans-local and virtual music scenes (Bennett & Rogers, 2016). Both DeNora’s framing of the musical event, as well as the concept of the music scene, emerged from cultural sociology, so in a way we can understand music scenes as clusters of related musical events.

Studies on queer scenes, including the work of Jodie Taylor (Taylor, 2012) and Tony Adams (Adams & Herrmann, 2020), are typically grounded in radical-deconstructionist approaches to understanding queerness, like those I mentioned before, and thus emphasise the politically-charged, performative and subversive aspects of these spaces. These studies offer rich insights into alternative ways of living and being in queer communities, but their relationship to discourses of health promotion needs to be questioned. A chapter by Tony Adams and Robin Boylorn (2016) for example, describes a queer fetish event called the “Belly Rub Weekend”, in Chicago, which was aimed at men who are deliberately seeking to gain weight, called “gainers”, and the men who encourage them. The authors write that, at this event, men discuss “weight gaining experiences and fantasies such as disregarding medical advice about expanding size... the joys of not fitting in desks at offices or airplanes... and wanting to become immobile and bedbound, all the while being fed by an encouraging boyfriend” (p. 93). The authors conclude that this event is “queer” because it offers possibilities of resistance and other ways of thinking, doing, living, and loving, and it, quote, “advocates beliefs and practices that others might find to be wrong” (p. 93). (Adams alters this quote in a subsequent chapter, giving, in place of “wrong”, “peculiar, inappropriate, incoherent, or disgusting”. See Adams & Herrmann, 2020, p. 233). Here we get some sense of a self-othering or self-marginalising tendency in radical queer theory, and its potential implications for health, where ignoring medical advice becomes a form of queerness.

Outside of radical queer theory, the health promotion of queer people has been addressed in a range of other ways. For example, in Alan Downs' powerful book *The Velvet Rage* (2006) the author offers an account of a common pathway that many gay men follow, which begins with hugely overwhelming experiences of shame and invalidation in childhood, through a second phase of excessive compensatory behaviours geared towards shame avoidance (even long after one has "come out") that may include perfectionism, the quest for acquisition and external validation, drug and alcohol abuse, and promiscuity. If one can manage the work, one arrives, hopefully, at a place of self-acceptance, authenticity and integrity, the result of a literal process of re-integrating the psychological aspects of one's "self" split apart in childhood. This third stage may continue to include practices like drug use and promiscuity, just no longer as shame-avoiding behaviours.

Downs doesn't pathologise gay men's experiences, but he does account for the institutional nature of them, and their psychological impacts. I have never seen myself in anything like I saw myself in that book. I was physically abused by a primary school teacher growing up for being way too feminine and obviously gay, and I was spat on, I was bashed, I was called names, and I felt alone in it most of the time. And when you're that young, you don't really say anything, because you feel ashamed. Growing up with a lesbian sister, who I'm very close to, has provided insight into how vastly different our stories are in this respect. So it became clear to me that the auto-ethnographic aspect of this research was going to be the backbone of it, a story of enduring attachment and connection to these gay (or queer?) venues and spaces that I have been frequenting for about 25 years, and which are all carefully scaffolded by music in particular ways so as to offer certain kinds of experience to queer people, noting that what "queer" actually means is, by definition, always up for grabs.

I've conducted 17 interviews by the time of writing, of between 1-3 hours in length, and the recruitment process for the interviews was multi-layered, relying on my personal social network within the community, as well as connections to specific venues and their staff who helped encourage and promote this research. It's important to clarify, here, that the intent is not to produce a representative sample that allows for generalisation. Rather, the aim is to provide an auto-ethnographic window into a world that I have inhabited for a long time, and the recruitment process reflected that. As such, many of the interviews have involved men who identify both as gay and as queer (some one or the other), but some bisexual men, lesbian women, and one person who identifies as trans-masculine and non-binary have also contributed their voices to this study. Interview participants are aged between 24 and 55, and they either own or manage venues, select or perform music in them, or they attend as patrons. The cultural

backgrounds of participants include Caucasian Australian, Middle Eastern, African, Pakistani, and British. None of the participants so far have identified as being disabled, and all live in Victoria. The various data sources are being woven into the broader autoethnography, and this is impacting the writing style. One participant, Sam, a man in his thirties of Middle Eastern descent, pleaded with me to not make this study a sop story about the trope of gay loneliness. “We have enough stories in popular culture about gay loneliness” he said; “gay men are superheroes—tell a story about that”. Humour as a coping strategy, and as a bid for dignity, has permeated the interviews, and I think the book this study will eventually become will actually end up being quite light-hearted and funny, at least at times, not because I need the validation of readers—I don’t do that anymore—but because that represents something about the truth of our experiences.

As I mentioned, the venues in question are mostly located in Collingwood, along Smith Street, Peel Street and Wellington Street, but the interview discussions have extended beyond this to the trans-local relationship between this local scene of bars and clubs and the broader, more radical queer scene, its manifestations in events like house parties across Melbourne, and even its ideological connections to cities like Berlin, where I lived for about 18 months during my early thirties. Almost all of the gay men I have interviewed acknowledged that a typical night out on this local Collingwood scene follows a reasonably precise progression, one that people can dip into and out of at their leisure, but rarely out of order. There is a gravity to this progression, a pull between this venue and the next, especially for gay men. And that is because, I think, the musical experiences on offer do particular kinds of work for gay men across different dimensions or levels of social connection. This doesn’t mean that other people, including other queer people, do not or should not use these spaces. But this project does rub against queer theorising about the material reality of male homosexuality, which is something that, in the course of conducting this research, I have been forced to reckon with, especially to the extent that it involves sex, kinship, and family (more on this below).

The early stages of this progression are typically more outward-looking, more queer in the radical sense, more conversational, and more performing-arts focused. Here, bodies move in relation to one another more-or-less as they do in able-bodied, polite society. This type of experience is associated with bars like The 86 and Mollies, where people might watch live cabaret or drag shows, or other live performances such as those that are part of Melbourne’s various festivals, or play bingo during the week, or watch screenings of RuPaul’s Drag Race on big TVs. Booths, chairs and tables face each other, and people talk. I interviewed the owner of The 86, Anthony, and we spoke about his work campaigning for marriage equality, hosting

campaign events in the bar, and how he aims to generate as much diversity in his bar as possible, for example, in his staff, and in the stage performers that he books. When it came to the music, he was obsessed. He described music as “the most significant element of the venue”. We talked about so much, but worth noting here is that he clearly feels duty bound to care for and preserve the canon of great queer songs, like “It’s Raining Men” (The Weather Girls, 1983), even though he knows his punters do not necessarily like them in a conscious way. He asked me, “How many [people] really like that song deep down? The answer is probably not so many. However, these songs become our anthems to reinforce it is our space. You don’t go to the Retreat Hotel in Brunswick and hear ‘It’s Raining Men’... So yeah, at times I’m like, fuck we have played [Kylie Minogue] so much, but it’s important that we keep playing it.” His music selections are informed by a concern for the imagined collective of which we are all a part, as queers.

In this typical progression, then follows a more concentrated, more sexual, dancefloor-disco-focused experience, in which bodies become closer, and modes of communication become more physical and less verbal. This is associated with bars and clubs like Circuit and The Peel, which both used to be sex-on-premises venues, and which retain a strong sexual intensity in their atmosphere. Several participants also talked about an event called Honcho Disko at The 86 and how it offered a joyful atmosphere for dancing without the intense undertone of sexual conquest. The music is typically some mixture of pop, disco, dance, or house, but, as Sam put it, the optimistic ideal is “disco, with a strong female lead vocal”. Another participant, Corey, a Caucasian Australian man in his thirties, described why this mattered, saying, “Well, it's got a good bit of bass in it. It's got like puh-puh-puh-puh beat [making hand gestures to demonstrate what the music is, with his body] which isn't too fast... [it] allows you to not only dance with yourself, it allows you to dance with others.”

When I asked him what was different about this kind of dancing, versus a waltz or a tango, or some other dance that involves other people, he said:

“First of all, you don't have a lot of space when you're on a dance floor in a gay bar. So it's very little on the arms... It's like an elbows in, palms up and out [kind of dance]. And you're probably holding a drink. So it's going to be in the hips and feet, and when it's centred in the hips and feet, that also means that you can connect with someone else's hips and feet, which can often lead to a pash [kiss], which is, like, the ultimate fling on the dance floor.”

In these settings, the space of social connection closes up, somewhat, in a musically scaffolded, and flirtatious, sexual movement towards physical intimacy.

Discussions typically arise at this point about whether any women in the group will continue partying into the evening with the gays. Often they do not, and I'll discuss some of the reasons why below, although this topic is very complex and warrants its own essay. But it's worth noting here that I interviewed the managing partner at Yah Yah's on Smith Street, a man called Nick (Caucasian Australian, in his thirties), which holds a weekly event called Thursgay. This event is aimed at a much younger crowd; Nick told me that about 80 percent of their audience is aged between 18 and 24, and that this group is much less likely to define themselves in terms of their sexuality rather than their gender. Nick reported that the audience at Yah Yah's finds their musical heroes in emerging queer artists like Chappell Roan. This point felt important, especially as we discussed the way sexuality, rather than gender, defines some gay men, especially some of us who came of age prior to the emergence of the internet and the development of drugs which prevent HIV transmission, such as PreP. This was only listed on the Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme in Australia (i.e. it became widely available) in 2018, when I was in my early thirties. Prior to this, being gay felt like a ticking time bomb, as if my sexuality was, perhaps ironically, the very thing that was going to kill me in the end.

For many gay men, the last stop on this typical journey through the scene is Wet on Wellington, a gay sauna 150 metres away from The Peel. Wet on Wellington is a totally sexually charged, sex-on-premises venue, and bodies could hardly be more intertwined. You are handed a towel and a locker key when you walk in, and inside you find a 25-metre lap pool, various saunas and steam rooms, a little bar, lots of showers, and a pitch-dark upstairs area entirely dedicated to facilitating sex. I've been there many times, and in many ways it recalls experiences of being in locker rooms in high school as a teenager, with a bursting adolescent body, desperate to catch a glimpse of a bulge or a bicep, but equally as desperate not to be caught doing so, knowing the violence that awaited you if you were. Nothing pulls on the mind quite like two irreconcilable and competing primal urges.

When I spoke with Corey about his experiences there, he struggled to discuss them without the safety buffer of humour in between himself and the topic, and I understood why. He said, "Well, for those listening at home [laughs]... it has a lovely spa, and it has a big, beautiful pool. It's got a lovely outdoor area. I've spent many times [there] rolling around in my grubby towel, bent out of my brains in the sun." When I asked him about the music, he said that it's just background noise to drown out the occasional moan. I asked him why he thought that was. He said, "The reason why I suspect it's like that is because you don't want any of the music that

you love ruined by a memory of you being railed by some dude in a sling. Music makes you remember things!”

“Why do you want to avoid the memories?” I asked him. He said,

“I don't mind being in that environment, and it'll take a very particular set of circumstances for me to confidently step through the door. Sometimes the behaviour is so depraved and out of character... I'm fine to have that as an experience that can be remembered vaguely on my own terms. I don't want it triggered when I'm walking through Myer [a local department store].”

We also talked about how, on the odd occasion, we do see women, or trans, or non-binary people in at Wet on Wellington. I recalled seeing a young non-binary person, whom I would have described as a woman by the way she looked, climbing into the spa with the rest of the men. The mood changed, and I wasn't sure how I felt about it. I asked Corey what he thought. He was typically hilarious and insightful, saying: “Actually, I saw a gender diverse person there a couple of months ago. So there were these big titties popping up in the spa, which I'd never seen in my life. So that was quite curious... But I'm like, whatever, in for a penny, in for a pound. You think that's weird? Come upstairs in a minute, I'll show you something weird.” I nearly died laughing.

We talked about a whole range of things, but the conversations with Corey and some of the other participants highlighted how extremely subtle musical shifts, such as shifts in the degree to which a melody is memorable or not, the degree to which it crystallises into a distinct shape or doesn't, could result in a breakdown of the social action that the music is affectively scaffolding.

Of course, not all gay men experience these spaces these ways, but many do. Another participant, Tom, told me that he was having sex with men in parks as a kid on his way to high school, years ago when he lived in Newcastle, and that he is still a long way off completing the emotional work that is needed to allow him to engage with these aspects of the scene in healthy ways. He said, “Yeah, I've still got a bit of a chip on my shoulder about beats and saunas and stuff. I still use them, I still go to them, but I don't know if it was the right way for a sixteen-year-old to start learning about the world.”

Of course, it can be empowering and progressive to push the limits of what can be considered sexually appropriate or acceptable. Queer theory has done a lot to explore that. But in this study, participants more often talked about an experience that is akin to the psychological

splitting Alan Downs (2006) described, a mental compartmentalisation and geographical distribution, across the scene, of aspects of one's "self", and, very often, deeply important aspects at that. Many of the participants reflected on the nature of their queerness and how it was similar, or different, from their homosexuality. Blake, for example, said:

"Queer[ness] is about subverting expectations or choosing to take a different path... I think you can meet some very heteronormative queer people, gay people... who don't want to be different... [But] in another way, it's not really fair to say if you decide that you want a permanent job and you want to buy a house and you want to have kids, that you're not queer... Maybe it just has to be about self-identification. It's just what you think you are."

As Sam, put it: "at least the meat-and-two-veg life"—meaning, the heteronormative, or homonormative life—"has guard rails".

In many ways, this project is an expression of compassion to the gay men in the study who are making their way along a sometimes very lonely journey back to themselves. It is shining a light on what social connection sometimes means in my world, and while it does focus on gay men in particular, it draws upon other voices as well, although this will be picked up in later publications. It also explores the sometimes very complicated relationship that gay men have with other members of the queer community, and those outside of it. The vectors of these complexities seemingly go in all directions, and a lot hinges on the idea of the "self", what people think it is, and the tension between the queer injunction, after Foucault, not to take sexual identity categories seriously (Foucault, 1990), and the reality of the sexual and sexualised constraints of male homosexual bodies.

A variety of forms of social connection are emerging in the research, and one of these is *kinship*. Nick told me, "When you step into that venue [Yah Yah's], you stepping into my house". Many of the young people who go to that venue unironically call him "dad", which, to his painful dismay, has attracted the ire of some others in the community who seem to imagine inappropriate sexual undertones. Some of the patrons who don't have anywhere else to go at Christmas, spend it with Nick at his apartment—"Gay Christmas!"—he calls it. Some of them have moved in with him, temporarily, because they would otherwise be without housing. Nick said, "My life was enriched because I have... like, I don't think I'll ever have kids, because I've already got too many, if that makes any sense. I don't need any more. They multiply every year."

Since my aim in this essay was to provide a glimpse into my world, and since I opened with an anecdote about my father's death, I want to finish with a story about the birth of a little boy, as a reflection on queer kinship. Almost one year ago to the day, my lesbian sister's partner gave birth to a beautiful boy, whom they named Vivian, with the help of my sperm donation. I had offered to help them start their family, in part because my sister knew not to ask me to be a donor for her partner. This was because she had personally helped me make sense of about ten years of complex and sometimes extremely difficult discussions and negotiations with women who had approached me about the possibility of a sperm donation. These discussions involved varying degrees of thoughtfulness, from a request in the form of a text message containing thirteen words, right up to deeply loving conversations that lasted years, which did not result in a pregnancy, but which did result in much stronger friendships. My sister had witnessed me struggle with this process of realising that a part of myself, which was only now coming into view, had lain dormant, and psychologically inaccessible to me, since the earliest years of my life, when I became intelligible to others as gay, and thus, socialised away from the idea of ever having my own family. She understood that gay men's prospects for family and kinship are often so far out of reach that they are almost unthinkable.

Gay men must overcome "countless barriers" (Carneiro et al., 2017, p. 8) to start their own families, and while altruistic surrogacy is an option in Australia, there are big ethical questions surrounding this mode of assisted reproduction, one of which is the fact that, in Victoria, surrogates can change their mind, after the child is born, about whether they will hand over the child to the intended parents (Everingham et al., 2014). Similarly, being a "known donor" means that donors do not become the legal parent of the child born from their sperm donation under Victorian law (Dempsey et al., 2019); the relationships of donors to donor-conceived children hinge almost entirely on the benevolence of the people to whom they donate, regardless of the good faith conversations that happen prior to donation. For me, as a gay man, the process of actually considering these options seriously only began once they became feasible, and that was when women started asking me for my sperm. I would think to myself, "We could do it, today—I could actually create a biological offspring. All I have to do is agree to do it." The magnitude of this new thought was enough to turn my life upside-down, but the precarity of the whole thing was, quite literally, unbearable to me. Radical queer theories about how sexual identity categories are merely the causes and effects of discourse just felt rude.

At the same time, a grieving process commenced, grief for the caring and loving part of myself that knew he had the potential to be a great father, and that he would probably love it, but which had been, for so long, terribly ignored and underdeveloped, partly because learning

to do that at an early age was a coping strategy that was psychologically necessary for me. I came to realise that many people, including gay men themselves, underestimate the social, financial, psychological and emotional hoops that they need to jump through before they can start to see themselves as active agents, let alone protagonists, in the creative project of kinship formation. It is only because of the trust I have in my sister and her partner, that they will honour and celebrate and help protect my relationship as a donor-uncle with Vivian, in the future, that I was able to find it in me to help them start their beautiful family. Ironically, I got what I wanted by *giving up* the identity of father, and it is this that gave me license to welcome him into the world, and to love him, which I do, deeply, at the same time as I let him go, and pass the identity of father to my beautiful, butch-lesbian, sister.

What could be queerer than that.

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